

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Germany: An Introduction

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The financial situation of local governments is critical in large parts of Germany. The budgets of many local governments are in the red and are leading to an increase in debt, which is why loans (*Kassenkredite*) are increasingly being used as a financing instrument for current expenditure. The reasons for this are manifold (financial crisis, economic decline, tax reforms, responsibility assignments by the federal and *Länder* governments, increase in investments in the social sector), but the consequence is clear: This development endangers the autonomous action and creative freedom of local governments.

The financial sovereignty is part of the guarantee of the right to local self-government under Article 28(2) of the Basic Law (BL). It guarantees the municipalities an independent income and expenditure management within the framework of an orderly budgetary system. At the core of this sovereignty are the principles of financial self-responsibility, which is made clear by sentence 3 of Article 28(2) BL: 'The guarantee of self-government shall include the basis of financial autonomy; it shall comprise the right of municipalities to a source of tax revenues that corresponds with the economic ability of the tax debtors [e.g. business tax – *Gewerbesteuer*], and the right to fix the rates at which these sources shall be taxed.' A central problem of the financial plight of the municipalities is the not cost-covering congestion of ever costlier tasks (*Aufgabenüberbürdung*) through the federal government. This is the opposite of the revocation of responsibilities (*Aufgabenzug*). Within the framework of the Federalism Reform I, this problem could be stopped or mitigated by the prohibition on the assignment of responsibilities (*Aufgabenübertragungsverbot*) in Article 84(1)(7) BL.

Municipalities earn their revenue mainly through two main instruments: Levies and financial allocations. Levies can be taxes (*Steuern*), contributions (*Beiträge*) or fees (*Gebühren*) which are based on the Local Tax Law (*Kommunalabgabengesetz*) of the respective Land. Financial allocations are based on the Financial Equalization Act of the respective Land and the financial constitutional provisions of the respective *Land* constitution. Taxes account for the largest share of revenue (40 per cent), followed by allocations (20 per cent) and fees/contributions (10 per cent).

Tax revenue can be generated by local authorities in the form of local excise and expenditure taxes. In this respect, the Local Tax Laws grant them the right to find taxes, provided that these taxes are not 'similar to taxes regulated by federal law'. Important examples of this type of tax are the amusement tax, the dog tax, the overnight stay tax and the tax on second homes. Concerning a second group of taxes, only the revenue sovereignty and not also the tax finding right lies with the municipalities. However, they have the possibility to determine the tax

burden of their inhabitants in relation to their financial needs by setting so-called assessment rates to a limited extent. This applies to real taxes (land tax and business tax). Article 106 (7)(1) BL obliges the *Länder* to pass on a certain share of their total share of the so-called community taxes (income tax, corporation tax and turnover tax) to the municipalities (municipal financial equalization).

There are also short-term financing instruments such as loans, donations or sponsoring. In addition, municipalities generate income from economic activity, including interest from leases, rentals, capital investments and the concession fee for the provision of public roads for the laying of supply lines. The participation of municipalities in general legal transactions, in particular the acquisition and sale of assets, is subject to various conditions regulated in the respective Municipal Code (*Gemeindeordnung*). The initiation of insolvency proceedings against the assets of a municipality is excluded by law.⁴⁴

The legal framework within which the municipalities exercise their revenue and expenditure sovereignty is formed by Budget System (*Haushaltswesen*). The legal basis for this can be found in the respective Municipal Code while the legal basis of the budget economy in the respective municipality is the budget by-law (*Haushaltssatzung*) which has to be adopted for each calendar year in the framework of the budget plan (*Haushaltsplan*). At the end of each year financial accounting (*Rechnungslegung*) has to be made, which is then subject to a so-called audit (*Rechnungsprüfung*).

The structure of the county finances follows the structure described for the municipalities in many areas, and there is also a precarious financial situation at this level. A county specific financing instrument of great economic and political importance is the county levy (*Kreisumlage*). It is levied by the counties on the municipalities belonging to the county which constitutes a fundamental, but constitutionally justified encroachment on the municipalities' guarantee of local self-government under Article 28(2) BL. There is often a dispute between the municipalities and counties about the legitimate amount of the county levy.

It is not possible to make a clear distinction between rural local governments (RLGs) and urban local governments (ULGs). ULGs usually have the advantage that they can cover a considerable portion of their financial needs with income from business tax because many companies settle in conurbations. Nevertheless, no general statement can be made about this as there are also ULGs with precarious financial situations. Dealing with financial issues is therefore an issue for both RLG and ULG.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Schwarting G, *Der Kommunale Haushalt* (5th edn, Erich Schmidt Verlag 2019)

⁴⁴ Compare for example Art 77 Bavarian Municipal Code.

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